

Synthesis, characterization and spectral studies of cobalt(II) complexes of ethyl and *t*-butyl esters of hydrazine carboxylic acid

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Abstract : Cobalt(II) complexes of the general compositions, $[\text{CoL}_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{L} = \text{NH}_2\text{NHCOOR}$; $\text{R} = \text{Et}$ or Bu^t ; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and NCS^-) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, spectroscopic techniques (UV-Vis, IR) and magnetic moment measurements. The low conductivity data of all the complexes suggest their non-electrolytic nature. The magnetic studies show the complexes to be high spin octahedral. On the basis of electronic spectral studies they are assigned tetragonally distorted octahedral stereochemistry. Various ligand field parameters have been evaluated.

Keywords : Cobalt(II) complexes, hydrazine carboxylic acid, spectral studies.

Introduction

N-Substituted hydrazine carboxylic acids, having four donor sites, have been found to function as bidentate ligands, coordination in most cases occurring through amino nitrogen and carboxylate oxygen. Apparently prompted by their potential similarity to amino acids, hydrazine carboxylic acid complexes have been studied by several groups and several transition metal complexes of these ligands have been synthesised, characterized and in few cases crystal structures¹⁻⁷ have been established.

A few compounds of substituted hydrazine carboxylic acid have also been found to possess biological activity⁸⁻¹⁰. The literature survey reveals that the esters of hydrazine carboxylic acid have not been investigated for their ligational behaviour. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the coordinating ability of ethyl and *t*-butyl esters of hydrazine carboxylic acid with cobalt(II) salts.

Experimental

The ligands ethyl and *t*-butyl esters of hydrazine carboxylic acid were products of Fluka, AG, Germany. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as

received. All solvents used were of standard/spectroscopic grade. The estimation of metal were done following the standard literature procedures^{11,12}. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined micro analytically. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on a vibrating sample magnetometer. The molar conductance of the complexes at mM dilution in DMSO solution were measured on a Direct Reading Conductivity meter-303 with a dip type conductivity cell at room temperature. Their IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer in KBr discs. The UV-Vis spectra were recorded in DMSO deuterated on a Beckman DU-64 spectrophotometer with quartz cells of 1 cm path length.

Synthesis of complexes :

To an alcoholic solution (16 mL) of the ligand (L) (2.0 mmol) was added dropwise an alcoholic solution (12 mL) of cobalt(II) chloride/cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate and CoX_2 where ($\text{X} = \text{Br}^-$, I^- , NCS^-) (1.0 mmol) with constant stirring. It is further stirred for about half an hour. A light coloured complexes were separated slowly on further concentration and on leaving nearly 24 h (Fig. 1). The crystalline complexes were filtered off, washed with 3-4 mL dry diethylether to remove excess of ligand and dried over P_4O_{10} .

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Preparation of CoX₂ :

For bromo, iodo and thiocyanato complexes alcoholic solution of KBr, KI or NH₄NCS, respectively stirred with alcoholic solution of cobalt(II) chloride for about 1 h over a magnetic stirrer and entire reaction mixture was concentrated to one third of its volume on a water bath. On cooling a white precipitate of potassium chloride/NH₄Cl was separated and was filtered off. The filtrate containing CoX₂ was used in the above reactions.

Fig. 1. The tentative structure of the complexes.

Results and discussion

The colors, melting points, elemental analysis and molar conductance of the complexes are listed in Table 1. The complexes are fairly stable and decomposed beyond 200 °C. The low molar conductance values suggest¹³, their non-electrolytic nature. The magnetic susceptibility data of these complexes are reported in Table 2. Octahedral cobalt(II) complexes maintain a large contribution due to ⁴T_{2g} ground term and exhibit magnetic moment in the range 4.8–5.6 B.M.^{14,15}. The magnetic moment of the complexes show that all are paramagnetic and have three unpaired electrons indicating thereby a high-spin octahedral configuration.

In the octahedral symmetry, the cobalt(II) ion having the ground term ⁴T_{1g} generally have two strong bands and sometimes one or two bands of weaker intensity. The first band, ν₁, assigned to the transition ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}, is usually found in the 1818–1000 nm region; the second band, ν₂, is a weak one but spin-allowed, assigned to the

transition ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g} and found in the 833–588 nm region; and the third band, ν₃, which is often split into two or three components, is assigned to the transition ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P), ²G, ²P and are usually found in the 625–454 nm region. In D_{4h} symmetry, however, the ν₁ band is observed to split into two components (⁴B_{2g}, ⁴E_g) to the extent depending upon the magnitude of distortion produced by the axial ligands. Further, in this symmetry^{16–21} the ν₃ band is also expected to split giving rise to the term ⁴A_{1g}, ⁴E_g (⁴T_{1g}(P) in octahedral field) and the ⁴B_{1g} transition (coming from ⁴A₂(F) octahedral field) is usually too weak to be observed.

In the electronic spectra of the complexes of ethyl and *t*-butyl esters of hydrazine carboxylic acid of cobalt(II), the splitting of ν₁ and ν₃, bands have been observed in all the cases, but for the **1** and **9** complexes, in which only ν₁ has been found to split. Thus except for these two complexes in all other cases four bands have been observed in the range 1375–1574 (ν₁), 1077–1165 (ν₂), 535–580 (ν₃) and 416–429 nm (ν₄) which have been assigned on the basis of D_{4h} symmetry. Following these assignments the calculations for the tetragonal parameters D_s and D_t have been made, using the equations suggested by Lever¹⁶. The evaluated data are recorded in Table 3. The order for increasing D_t is thus -

The values of $d\pi = \pi(\text{anion}) - \pi(\text{L})$ where π (anion) and π (ligand) are defined as π antibonding properties of the ligands, on the Z-plane and XY-plane. The quantity of $d\sigma = \sigma(\text{anion}) - \sigma(\text{L})$; where σ (anion) and σ (L) are defined as σ antibonding interaction of the ligands on the Z- and XY-planes, respectively.

IR spectra :

The main IR bands and their assignments are listed in Table 4. Assignments of absorption in the 3300–3000 cm⁻¹ region to -N-H stretching frequencies is beyond doubt. It is apparent from the available data^{22,23} that the coordination of amines lowers the N-H stretching frequency by about 100 cm⁻¹. It has been proposed that this lowering of N-H stretching frequency upon coordination is due to the drainage of electrons from the nitrogen atom to the metal ion which in terms weakens the N-H₂ bond. In the ethyl ester of hydrazine carboxylic acid, only one

Table 1. Analytical data on cobalt(II) complexes of ethyl and *t*-butyl ester of hydrazine carboxylic acid

Comps.	Formula weight	Color	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Conductivity Λ_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
				Co	C	H	N	
1	390.93	Pink	200d ^a	15.0 (15.1)	18.1 (18.4)	3.9 (4.0)	21.6 (21.4)	3.6
2	337.93	Pink	199	17.4 (17.5)	21.1 (21.3)	4.6 (4.7)	16.7 (16.5)	2.9
3	425.73	Pink	205	13.7 (13.8)	16.3 (16.8)	3.6 (3.7)	13.3 (13.1)	3.6
4	520.73	Light pink	200d ^a	11.3 (11.4)	13.7 (13.8)	2.9 (3.0)	10.3 (10.7)	4.2
5	324.90	Dark pink	200d ^a	15.3 (15.4)	24.8 (25.0)	4.0 (4.1)	22.3 (21.9)	4.3
6	444.90	Pink	210	13.2 (12.8)	26.4 (26.6)	5.2 (5.3)	19.1 (18.6)	3.6
7	392.40	Light pink	205	15.0 (14.6)	29.9 (30.2)	5.9 (6.0)	13.6 (14.1)	2.8
8	478.90	Onion pink	200d ^a	11.7 (12.0)	24.5 (24.9)	4.8 (4.9)	11.3 (11.6)	4.1
9	572.9	Light pink	210	10.2 (10.4)	12.5 (12.8)	3.8 (4.0)	9.7 (9.9)	4.2
10	378.90	Deep pink	210	13.4 (13.2)	32.6 (32.8)	5.3 (5.4)	20.0 (19.1)	4.3

^aDecompose.

Where **1** ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{10}\text{Co}$), **2** ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{Co}$), **3** ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Co}$), **4** ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{I}_2\text{Co}$), **5** ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{SCo}$), **6** ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{10}\text{Co}$), **7** ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{Co}$), **8** ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Co}$), **9** ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{I}_2\text{Co}$), **10** ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{SCo}$).

Table 2. Magnetic data of cobalt(II) complexes of ethyl and *t*-butyl ester of hydrazine carboxylic acid

Comps.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$	Temp. (T + 273) K	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
1	2.19	298	857.26	1008.28	4.46
2	2.49	298	841.42	1008.50	4.52
3	1.95	298	833.64	1008.73	4.58
4	1.59	300	832.83	1009.13	4.70
5	2.15	298	826.60	1008.88	4.62
6	1.81	300	809.84	1008.30	4.48
7	2.02	300	794.23	1008.75	4.60
8	1.63	300	786.53	1009.05	4.68
10	2.77	301	779.11	1008.83	4.63

band is observed at 3300 cm^{-1} , whereas *t*-butyl ester of hydrazine carboxylic acid shows a shoulder in addition to a band at 3300 cm^{-1} and 3200 cm^{-1} .

In the cobalt(II) complexes of these ligands, usually two infrared bands appears in this region, which are at lower frequency than in the free ligand. This clearly sug-

gests the coordination nitrogen atom of the primary amino group of the ligands. The NH_2 bending deformation vibration has been assigned to the band observed at about 1000 cm^{-1} in the complexes as well as in the ligands²³.

The presence of a band at about 1000 cm^{-1} in the complexes has been taken as an evidence of chelated N–N group^{24,25}. The carbonyl stretching frequencies provide a very important clue in the elucidation of the structure. In an unionised carboxylate group, the carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) stretching vibration appears at about 1700 cm^{-1} . The antisymmetric stretching vibration of a carboxylate group is known to be particularly sensitive to the mode of coordination. As the covalent character of M–O bond increases, the antisymmetric stretching frequency also increases.

A perusal of Table 4 indicate the presence of only one carbonyl stretching frequency at 1700 cm^{-1} in the ethyl and *t*-butyl esters of hydrazine carboxylic acid. This band is considerably reduced in the cobalt(II) complexes indicating the coordination of carbonyl oxygen to cobalt(II).

Table 3. Electronic spectral data (nm) of cobalt(II) complexes with ethyl and *t*-butyl ester of hydrazine carboxylic acid and calculated ligand field parameters

Compds.	Observed bands (nm) and assignments					Calculated ligand field parameters						
	$T_{2g} \rightarrow$					D_q (E)	D_q (A)	D_t	$-D_s$	$(d\pi-d\sigma)$	$d\sigma$	$d\pi$
	${}^4B_{2g}(v_1)$	${}^4E_g(v_1)$	${}^4B_{1g}(v_2)$	${}^4E_g(v_3)$	${}^4E_{2g}(v_3)$							
1	1546	1144	-	484	-	1180	731	260	-	1130	1745	2850
2	1374	1080	609	537	424	1120	725	225	1266	990	1475	2465
3	1429	1109	580	539	422	1135	730	231	1335	1005	1570	2576
4	1405	1084	-	549	424	1140	725	242	1384	1052	1625	2675
5	1572	1155	600	580	424	1225	760	265	1657	1155	1992	3147
6	1571	1166	664	547	420	1195	755	250	1432	1105	1672	2775
7	1378	1080	-	535	429	1120	725	230	1142	1000	1280	2285
8	1439	1109	610	539	419	1130	720	235	1368	1035	1607	2640
9	1400	1088	-	480	1150	721	245	-	1070	1630	2705	-
10	1544	1144	655	578	424	1220	770	260	1650	1125	1995	3120

Table 4. IR spectral bands (cm^{-1}) of cobalt(II) complexes with ethyl and *t*-butyl esters of hydrazine carboxylic acid

Compds.	ν_{asym} (NH_2)/ sym NH_2	ν_{NH}	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu(\text{N-N})$	Co-N	Co-O	Co-X (X = Cl^- , Br^-)
L	3440/3300	3200	1770	1040	-	-	-
L'	3400/3300	3220	1700	1045	-	-	-
1	3420/3280	3100	1720	980	410	520	-
2	3370/3250	3110	1720	1015	410	515	250
3	3400/3280	3090	1650	1018	408	510	220
4	3380/3270	3110	-	1020	405	510	-
5	3400/3250	3100	1660	1020	370	509	-
6	3350/3250	3120	-	1020	415	515	-
7	3350/3280	3110	1720	1020	415	510	250
8	3350/3258	3100	1700	1020	415	515	220
9	3350/3270	3105	1700	1015	415	515	-
10	3350/3260	3100	1700	1020	370	520	-

Where L ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$), L' ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$).

A band of medium intensity observed around 250 cm^{-1} in **2** and **7** complexes has been assigned to Co-Cl stretching vibration²¹. In the spectra of bromo complexes of the metal under discussion, the band appearing at about 220 cm^{-1} has been assigned to Co-Br stretching vibration. Co-I stretching vibration has not been observed since this band is expected below 200 cm^{-1} . A *trans* arrangement of halogens, with respect to each other, is suggested on the basis of only one band appearing for each Co-X vibration, since for a *cis* configuration more than one band is expected²⁶⁻³⁰. Similar bands at 1460 cm^{-1} (ν_4), 1430 cm^{-1} (ν_1), and 1020 cm^{-1} (ν_2), and a separation of 30 cm^{-1} for ($\nu_4-\nu_1$) observed in the infrared spectra of the complex of **6** indi-

cate the monodentate nature of the coordinated nitrate groups.

Thus the overall infrared spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes of ethyl and *t*-butyl esters of hydrazine carboxylic acid reveal that the ligands behave as bidentate ones binding the cobalt(II) through amino nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen atoms.

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